

IDENTIFICATION OF TASKS REQUIRED FOR SOUND SYSTEM OPERATION FOR INCLUSION IN TECHNICAL TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMME IN NIGERIA

¹Legborsi Nwineh, ²Thankgod Okani Ayabatonye John-Tuwei, ³Paulinus Chijioke Okwelle

^{1,3}Department of Vocational and Technical Education
Rivers State University, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria

²XAYAMACA Technologies Limited, Port-Harcourt, Nigeria

Correspondence author email: nwineh.legborsi@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This exploratory sequential mixed method study aimed at identifying tasks required for effective system operation by sound technicians. A sample of 10 sound system experts were purposively selected for the qualitative phase and 30 for the quantitative phase of the study. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through closed and open-ended questionnaire. The instrument for quantitative data was subjected to internal consistency reliability test using Cronbach Alpha which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.62 for the set up component, 0.83 for the monitoring component and 0.85 for the maintenance component. Thematic analysis was used to analyse qualitative data while percentages and frequency count were used to analyse quantitative data. The study found that tasks required for setting up sound system included site inspection, selection and preparation of equipment, mobilization of personnel and equipment, installation of equipment among others. Tasks involved in monitoring sound system included: monitoring of control console/control room and monitoring of production output. Tasks involved in maintenance included: identification of faults and faulty equipment among others. It was recommended that identified tasks should be incorporated in programmes of instruction for Technical Education in tertiary institutions. Training for instructors, teachers and lecturers was recommended.

Keywords: Sound system operation, Sound system monitoring, Technical teacher education.

Introduction

Sound system operation is an integral and important aspect of information transmission in the broadcast media. In radio and television broadcasting, sound reproduction and recording studios, during live performance occasions such as theatres, in gatherings, of people requiring voice enhancement such as religious meetings, political rallies and sporting activities among others, sound system operation is needful to ensure

effective and efficient communication. In addition, activities of sound system operation are useful in business enterprise that trade in acoustic devices and equipment such as public address systems. In sound system operation, acoustic devices such as microphones, amplifiers, loud speakers and mixers are used for reproducing and refining audio quality, to enable effective communication between the source of information and audience located at far

distances particularly in large gatherings (Locsin, 2019).

In Nigeria, technical teacher education is a type of teacher education programme that primarily prepares technical teachers who after graduation are expected to teach trade subjects such as electrical/electronic trades, mechanical trades building trades and others in technical colleges and other technical schools at the secondary level (Akaninwor, 2010). The programme is majorly provided by colleges of education, teacher training colleges, universities and some polytechnics that have or school of education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2014; UNESCO-UNEVOC, 2019; Uwaifo & Uwaifo, 2009). Activities and operations of universities are regulated by National University Commission (NUC). Activities of colleges of education are regulated by National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) while activities of polytechnics and technical colleges are regulated by National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). These regulating agencies develop curriculum or programmes of instruction that serves as benchmark for the different institutions they regulate (Abdulwahab & Sa'i, 2014).

In the curriculum of technical colleges for the programme titled, "Radio, TV & Electronic Work", one of the modules students are supposed to take, for a period of four weeks, is acoustic devices/equipment. Within this period, students are to learn among other things, how to set up, operate and maintain sound system devices such as public address system and acoustic devices including amplifiers, microphones and

loudspeakers (National Board for Technical Education, 2001, p. 42). Students of technical teacher education, particularly those in the subject area of electrical/electronics are prepared to teach "Radio, TV and Electronic Works" in technical colleges, of which learning how to setup, operate and maintain acoustic devices/equipment is part. Consequently, they should be exposed to instruction both theory and practical to equip them with the competencies they need to deliver effective instruction on these topics if they find themselves in technical colleges.

Statement of the Problem

Although, setting up, operating and maintaining sound system is important for technical teacher education students in general and electrical/electronics education students in particular. It is however observed from the curriculum of instruction prepared by National University Commission (NUC) and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) for technical teacher education, that the topic acoustic devices/equipment or its related content such as setting up, operating and maintaining/ troubleshooting public address system (P.A.S.) is not spelt out as a topic students of technical teacher education should offer. Since this content is not spelt out, it is not clear the extent, in terms of depth and breadth, lecturers and instructors who provide instruction for technical teacher education in colleges of education and universities will treat this important topic if at all it is treated. And it is not clear as well, if what is covered will make the students competent enough to deliver instruction on this topic

in technical colleges for which they are being prepared. If technical teacher education students are not exposed to lessons on these acoustic devices/equipment, there is the tendency that they may be ill prepared to teach this topic in technical colleges.

Purpose and Significance of the Study/ Research Questions

This article is part of a research study initiated to develop an instructional package to aid instruction in the topic of sound system operation. Specifically, the aim of this aspect of the research was to identify tasks required to carry out effective sound system operation, with the view to aid curriculum planners and developers, gain knowledge of tasks involved in sound system operation. With such knowledge they could develop objectives to help lecturers and instructors of colleges of education and universities as well as technical colleges tailor instruction to help students acquire required competencies in sound system operation. To achieve this aim of identifying tasks involved in sound system operation, the following research questions were answered.

1. What are the tasks involved in setting up sound system?
2. What are the tasks involved in monitoring sound system?
3. What are the tasks involved in maintaining sound system?

Literature/Conceptual Framework

Sound system, also regarded as public address system is a system that

electronically amplifies and distributes sound to reach a large population of public with the aid of components such as microphone, equalizer, mixer, amplifier, limiter and loudspeaker among others (Ministry of Railways, Government of India, 2012 & Solomon, 2018). Sound system operation comprises setting up, monitoring and maintaining the equipment for effective communication between the sound source and the audience (Bureau of Labor Statistics, United States Department of Labor, 2019; Truity, 2019). Setting up a sound system involves making arrangement to ensure that the system is up, running and ready for an event. Monitoring involves using the loudspeaker or earphones to judge the sound production from the system. Any issues identified during this activity is then controlled with the help of the mixer in a process regarded as control (Nisbett, 2003). Maintenance involves all the actions taken to prolong the life of a thing (Ogbuanya, 2009).

Although, a number of documents exist in the literature that describe equipment involved in sound system operation and public address system, specific information about tasks requirement for setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound systems which could help a lecturer and instructor in developing lecture or a curriculum planner in developing objectives on the topic is lacking in the literature. For example, Mega Public Address System (2018) provides information about types of public address system. One document was found that describes the setup of a public address system for a stadium arrangement by a proprietary public address system, parts-express (2016). However, the document only describes consideration for the

location, assembling/ mounting equipment, running cables, connecting amplifiers to speakers and testing. Other components that may be included in sound system setup such as mixers were not described. Ministry of Railways, Government of India (2012) provides some specific and vital information about requirement when working with public address system with regard to connection of different equipment such as amplifier 350 watt and booster amplifier 500 watt. This document by Ministry of Railways, Government of India also provides information on maintenance of different elements (equipment) of a public address system but information regarding task involved in conducting maintenance exercise on a sound system while in operation which is one focus of this study was lacking. Information on setting up an entire system for an event was also lacking in the document. Eisele (2019) provides information about sound system design and setup for a crowd ranging from 300 to 500 persons. Information provided include speaker selection and positioning, mixer and microphone requirement. The document was void of information to guide one in the tasks involved in setting up the entire system for operation. This gap in literature necessitated this study which intended to identify the tasks needed for setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound system (i.e. public address system, while in operation) with the view to enhance the capacity of curriculum planners, lecturers and instructors both in colleges of education and universities who prepare vocational teachers for technical colleges and also to teachers of technical colleges in their instructional delivery process on the topic of public address system found

in the curriculum for Radio, Television and Electronic Works for technical colleges.

Methodology

This study employed exploratory sequential mixed method design. It is a type of mixed method research design in which the research is conducted in two phases. In the first phase, qualitative approach is employed, while in the second phase, quantitative research approach is employed to test for relationships among variables or test hypotheses identified or formulated in the first phase of the research. Furthermore, in situations where an instrument of measure is not available, exploratory sequential design is used for the development of an instrument from the findings of the qualitative phase and then using a quantitative phase to ascertain the generalizability of such findings on the larger sample of participants (Creswell, 2012; Gay, Mills & Airasian, 2012; Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2006).

The population frame for this study covered audio/sound system professionals from the broadcast and media industry, radio and television sound engineers and technicians, church sound engineers and technicians together with sound system service providers in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State, Nigeria. The qualitative phase of the study utilised purposive sampling technique to select ten (10) sound system practitioners who have been involved in setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound systems to serve large audience of 500 persons and above. Purposive sampling was also utilized in the quantitative phase of the study to select

thirty (30) sound system operatives who have technical knowledge of sound systems, particularly systems used in public address systems.

An instrument titled, “Tasks Involved in Sound System Operation Open-Ended Questionnaire (TISSOOEQ)” was used to collect qualitative data. The sound system practitioners were requested to write freely concerning tasks involved in setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound system. Another instrument titled, “Tasks Involved in Sound System Operation Closed-Ended Questionnaire (TISSOCEQ)” was used to collect quantitative data which was structured on a 4-point rating scale with response options SA (for Strongly Agree); A (for Agree); D (for Disagree) and SD (for Strongly Disagree). It also comprised three components which elicited responses on the task for setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound system. These instruments were face validated by three experts. The instrument for quantitative data was subjected to internal consistency reliability test to obtain reliability coefficients of 0.62 for the setup component, 0.83 for the monitoring component and 0.85 for the maintenance component through Cronbach Alpha. The open-ended questionnaire was labelled (coded): RESP 1 to RESP 10 meaning respondent 1 to respondent 10. Thematic analysis was employed to identify themes from the qualitative data to gain understanding of the tasks needed for setting up, monitoring and maintaining sound system. Creswell and Clark (2018) describe thematic analysis as a method used to analyse qualitative data. The quantitative data collected were analysed using percentages and frequency counts.

Findings

This section presents the findings of the study based on the research questions. For each research question, qualitative findings are presented first followed by quantitative results.

Research Question 1: What are the tasks involved in setting up sound system?

Findings from the qualitative phase of the study reveal that one major task involved in setting up a sound system is site inspection. Another task is selection of equipment followed by arrangement of stage, determination of the power requirement for sound system installation followed by dismantling of equipment for storage. In respect of this, one research participant wrote:

The set-up tasks include ... site inspection, choose and prepare the right type of equipment, arrange stage, check for total power capacity of the system... on completion, the system is decommissioned and moved to the storage (RESP 3).

Another participant commented:

The following tasks required for safe and effective sound system operation by sound technicians: site survey, equipment selection, set up at site (RESP 5).

Site inspection was considered very necessary and part of the very first things to do in trying to set up a sound system. This is because during this task, the sound technician will get to know the nature of the venue, whether indoor or outdoor activity is intended. Site inspection was also aimed at ascertaining the direction of wave, number of participants expected.

Such information would inform the kind of equipment employed and the power requirement for the system. This is expressed in the comments of some of the research participants.

Site survey is conducted to determine the direction of air flow, anticipated audience population, nature of venue: is it indoor or outdoor or semi-closed like a stadium (RESP 6).

Similarly, another participants stated:

In the event of sound system set up, inspection of the venue, should be put into consideration first. During the site inspection we consider the following: location (indoor/outdoor), direction of wind, audience population to determine the number of probable participants (RESP 9).

The findings from the participants also show that after site inspection, as explained by one research participant (RESP 10), the next task for the sound technician is selection of equipment and mobilization. According to this participant, equipment to be selected depend on the nature of the venue. A list of the equipment was provided by one participant (RESP 5) for an indoor programme with a capacity of about 500 persons and below. The equipment include: 4-5 power amp based on the watt, 2 pairs of 2 in 1 base speakers, 16 channels mixer, 3 pairs of full range, 1 GEQ, 1 speaker management, microphones and 4 monitor with low frequency. For an outdoor or semi-closed venue such as a stadium requiring a larger crowd, the equipment list include: 12 power amp based on the watt, 8 pairs of 2 in 1 base speakers, 32 channels mixer, full set of line array with stand, 9 pairs of

full range/raiser above 4ft, 5 GEQ, 6 speaker management, microphones, monitor with low frequency and 32 channel audio link. Following selection of equipment is mobilization; that is mobilization of both persons and equipment to the event site. When the equipment and persons have been mobilized to site, the connection of equipment begins with activities such as running of cables, terminating speakers, amplifiers, connecting all the channels to mixer. Typical illustration to this is provided thus:

...Another task is to arrange the stage by positioning the stage monitors. Run cables neatly and terminate to speakers, amplifiers and link all the channels to the mixer which is the control console (RESP 1).

Aside the above tasks of site inspection to determine its nature and the equipment requirement, selection/mobilization and connection of equipment, another task to ascertain the power requirement of the system. The finding from the study reveals that power supply requirement of the sound system is determined from knowing the power rating of sound system. As viewed by RESP 2, after connecting all the equipment, the power rating of the system is measured to ascertain the needed power which will inform power upgrade or not. When this has been ascertained, the system can be powered on.

Also, as part of the set up task, when the system has been powered on, another task is pre-programme sound check. Activities involved in this pre-programme check are

specified by one of the research participants as follows:

...Check for total power capacity of the system. Power the system and switch on the amplifiers and the control console. Use either computers with music to do pre-programme sound check. Additionally, use microphones to be used, for the pre-event sound check in readiness for the main event. It should be noted that this activity is done at least 24hrs before the event to enable correct anomalies should there be any (RESP 3).

This pre-programme sound system check from the findings, ensures that the stage is set for the intended event. During this check according to one respondent (RESP 6), the sound system technician identifies possible equipment or sections that could

hamper on smooth transmission during the event proper.

The last task involved in set up is to disassemble the equipment for storage at the end of the event. This was illustrated by one participant as follows:

...On completion, the system is decommissioned and moved to the storage (RESP 3).

This task of disassembling the equipment was viewed by the research participant 10 (RESP 10) as an important task during which cables are disconnected and rolled, equipment and other devices removed from risers, stands and moved back to the truck for onward transportation back to their base for storage.

The results of the quantitative phase of the study for research question 1 is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Tasks Involved in Setting up Sound System

S/N	The following are tasks for setting up sound system	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Inspect venue to know its nature (indoor or outdoor)	24	80.0	6	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
2	Inspect venue to determine audience population.	22	73.3	7	23.3	1	3.3	0	0.0
3	Inspect venue to know wave direction.	14	46.7	16	53.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
4	Inspect venue to know required equipment.	10	34.5	16	55.2	3	10.3	0	0.0
5	Select right equipment.	24	80.0	6	20.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
6	Move personnel and equipment to location.	17	56.7	13	43.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
7	Connecting equipment.	16	53.3	14	46.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
8	Ascertain Power requirement.	16	53.3	13	43.3	1	3.3	0	0.0
9	Power on/Pre-operation sound check of system 24hrs before event.	20	66.7	8	26.7	2	6.7	0	0.0
10	Decommission of equipment for storage.	18	62.1	10	34.5	1	3.4	0	0.0

Field Study, 2019

As shown in Table one, the responses from sound system operatives show that over 90% of them agreed that the listed

items (items 1-10) are tasks required for setting up a sound system. This shows that there is a similarity between the

qualitative findings and quantitative results.

Research Question 2: What are the tasks involved in monitoring sound system?

Findings from the qualitative phase of the study reveal that two major tasks are involved in monitoring a sound system. These tasks include: monitoring of control console/control room and monitoring of production output.

The findings obtained show that monitoring of control console/control room comprise other sub tasks as expressed in the responses by some research participants shown below.

The system must be constantly monitored in order to operate optimally during the event or programme. In order to achieve this goal, there must be constant system functionality check by doing the following; Check input signal on the console. Check output signal on the console, check frequency of the system, check for gain, check for modulation for amplifiers and graphic equalizers, check for output signal with headphone, check for production output on speakers, move around to check for system sound production. Use decibel or noise reduction meter to check for proper decibel for human earing. Use feedback monitor for man on

console to monitor system sound production (RESP 1).

In addition to this description, another participant added:

...Apart from the man on the control console, other technical crew members move around during the event to give feedback of the total system audio production to enable the audience hear audibly. To have significant audio output level, the decibel or noise reduction meter is used to measure the acceptable audio level output at about 90Db-8hrs, 110dB-1/day, which cannot be measured by mere listening (RESP 3).

The views of the participants reveal the component parts of the two major tasks involved in monitoring sound system. For example, checking of input and output signals as well as frequency on the console, checking of decibel level among others.

The results of the quantitative phase of the study for research question 2 is shown in Table 2.

Results in Table two above show that the responses from sound system operatives show that over 90% of them agreed that the listed items (items 11-20) are tasks required for monitoring a sound system. This shows that there is a similarity between the qualitative findings and quantitative results.

Table 2: Tasks Involved in Maintenance Sound System

S/N	The following are tasks for monitoring sound system	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Check input signal on the console.	22	73.3	8	26.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
2	Check output signal on the console.	23	76.7	7	23.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
3	Check frequency of the system.	15	50.0	15	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
4	Check for gain.	13	43.3	17	56.7	0	0.0	0	0.0
5	Check for modulation on amplifiers and graphic equalizers.	18	60.0	12	40.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
6	Check for output signal with headphone.	13	43.3	15	50.0	2	6.7	0	0.0
7	Check for production output on speakers.	17	56.7	12	40.0	1	3.3	0	0.0
8	Move around to check for system sound production.	17	56.7	12	40.0	1	3.3	0	0.0
9	Use decibel or noise reduction meter to check for proper decibel for human hearing.	8	27.6	17	58.6	3	10.3	1	3.4
10	Use feedback monitor for man on console to monitor system sound production.	14	46.7	16	53.3	0	0.0	0	0.0

Field Study, 2019

Research Question 3: What are the tasks involved in maintenance sound system?

Findings from the qualitative phase of the study reveal that maintenance is an integral task in sound system operation. Typical tasks involved in maintenance of sound system include: identification of fault and faulty equipment which is achieved during monitoring exercise, removing and replacing faulty equipment, troubleshooting faulty equipment among others. This is illustrated by the response of one research participant as follows:

Maintaining the sound system is as important as the set-up and monitoring. Note that no system can properly function without maintaining the parts or equipment, as there is always defective or faults associated with such equipment

while in operations. In view of this, spare equipment and accessories are provided to take care of sudden break-downs. On detection of any faulty defective component, such is isolated and replaced immediately by the technical crew within the shortest possible time. The faulty equipment is taken to the maintenance personnel in the team to test, troubleshoot and carry out repairs where applicable in readiness for re-use (RESP 3).

The above description of task involved in maintenance is similar to the view given by another research participant that:

Maintenance of sound system in operation is a bit simple because the whole system cannot get bad at the same time except power failure

issue or others such as; no output from the console which can be traced and rectified. However, operators of the system are more concerned with individual modules malfunctioning or becoming defective while in operation. This is the reason for the provision of spare or extra equipment. When detected the defective equipment is removed and replaced as quickly as possible. The equipment recovered is then sent to the maintenance personnel for testing, troubleshooting and

repair or maintained to be kept as standby equipment for future use (RESP 4).

Maintenance is viewed by RESP 10 as a task that ensures the sound system set up functions optimally while in operation. It ensures avoidance of frustration on the part of the sound technician and programme organizers. There is therefore need for regular maintenance. Quantitative result for research question 3 is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Tasks Involved in Maintenance Sound System

S/N	The following are tasks for maintenance of sound system	SA		A		D		SD	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1	Provide spare equipment	19	65.5	8	27.6	1	3.4	1	3.4
2	Remove and replace faulty equipment	21	70.0	7	23.3	2	6.7	0	0.0
3	Send faulty equipment to maintenance personnel in the team	15	50.0	15	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
4	Conduct test, diagnose problem and fix faulty equipment	17	56.7	11	36.7	2	6.7	0	0.0

Field Study, 2019.

As shown in Table 2 above, the responses from sound system operatives show that over 90% of them agreed that the listed items (items 21-24) are tasks required for setting up a sound system. This shows that there is a similarity between the qualitative findings and quantitative results.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one sought to ascertain the tasks involved in setting up sound system. The findings from the qualitative phase of the study corroborate that of the quantitative phase. Both phases reveal that task involved in setting up sound system include: site inspection, selection of equipment, movement of equipment to

venue, connection of equipment, determination of the power requirement, powering of the system, pre-event test and decommissioning of equipment. These findings align with that of Eisele (2019) that the choice of speakers and other sound reinforcement equipment should be based on coverage requirements and the size of the venue either indoor or outdoor, which corroborate the need to survey to ascertain the tasks involved in the setup of the sound system. Crofts (2019) in his view, asserted that for outdoor venues, there are certain variables to consider, such as the date, exact location and nature of the event (stage concert, arena display, etc.), load-out times, whether the performers will be on stage or grass,

covered or in open air, vehicle accessibility, among others.

Research question two sought to ascertain the tasks involved in monitoring a sound system. The findings from the qualitative phase of the study agree with that of the quantitative phase. Tasks involved in monitoring sound system include: monitoring of console and monitoring of production output. These two tasks were broken down into sub tasks including check for input signal on the console, check for output signal on the console, check for frequency of the system, check for gain, check for modulation on amplifiers and graphic equalizers under monitoring of console and check for output signal with headphone, check for production output on speakers, moving around to check for system sound production, using decibel or noise reduction meter to check for proper decibel for human hearing, use of feedback monitor for man on console under monitoring of output. This finding is in line with the view of Crofts (2012) that while the system is in operation, there should be checks on the console and the team members should walk around the whole audience to spot any imbalance in sound levels that is the audio output production of the system. He also asserted that this process continues throughout the duration of the events. Tapia and Lyons (2016) observed that the steps taken to monitor the sound system is to produce flawless audio for the audience, emphasizing that a system's sound quality is only as good as its weakest link, so providing clear, high fidelity audio at the inputs is the key to consistent success. They further noticed that volume (gain) controls are the simplest form of audio processor, used to

calibrate the gain structure of the system by aligning the levels of the various devices involved. There are two primary types of volume control: gain controls and attenuators. From the microphone input to the loudspeaker output, volume controls are found throughout the sound system. Most offer continuously variable adjustments using rotary knobs (potentiometers) or sliding faders. Gain control, also called trim control, adds amplification to the signal to align the microphone's or input instrument's output to the sensitivity of the input channel. An attenuator is a subtractive device that is used strictly for reducing the amount of signal allowed to pass through. Their positions support the tasks associated with the monitoring as describe in the study during the operation of a sound system.

Research question three sought to ascertain the tasks involved in maintaining a sound system. The findings from the qualitative phase of the study agree with that of the quantitative phase. Tasks involved in maintaining sound system include: identification of fault and faulty equipment which is achieved during monitoring exercise, removing and replacing faulty equipment, troubleshooting faulty equipment among others. This finding corroborates the view of Palme (2019) that maintenance of the components of the sound system should be carried out regularly before it is put into use. He also considered that faulty equipment be isolated and removed from service and replaced with functional ones to keep sound system work perfectly. Foster (2019) identified key areas in the tasks of maintenance of the sound system, which are providing replacement components, repair kits, test

instrument and the use of appropriate tools. He also observed that safety be put into account when repairs and maintenance work is carried out on the sound system and its components. According to Tayal (2012) touring sound systems have to be powerful and versatile enough to cover many different rooms, often being of many different sizes and shapes. They also need to use "field-replaceable" components such as speakers, horns, and fuses, which are easily accessible for repairs during a tour.

Conclusion

Knowledge of tasks required for sound system operation is needed by students of technical teacher education for effective instructional delivery on the topic of sound system devices such as public address system and acoustic devices in technical colleges and related schools. Qualitative and quantitative findings of this study revealed subtasks required for setting up, monitoring and maintenance as depicted by the concept map shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Task Require for Sound System Operation

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Programmes in Universities and Colleges of Education as well as Technical Colleges offering Electrical/Electronics should update their content to include instruction to cover these tasks involved in setting up, monitoring and maintenance of sound system.

2. Training should be organised for lecturers and instructors involved in providing instructions on sound systems in Universities and Colleges of Education and technical colleges should be organised by government, and the management of the institutions in order to update and enhance the capacity of the lecturers and instructors in instructional delivery in sound system operation

References

- Abdulwahab, S. & Sa'i, R.H. (2014). Refocusing technical teachers' education programmes towards youth empowerment. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 19(10), 69-73.
- Akaninwor, K.I.G. (2010). *Industrial education and technology in Nigeria: Development and current trends* (3rd ed). Odesaa Press, Owerri, Nigeria.
- Bureau of Labour Statistics, U.S. Department of Labour (2019). *Occupational outlook handbook, broadcast and sound engineering technicians*. Retrieved from <https://www.bls.gov/ooh/media-and-communication/broadcast-and-sound-engineering-technicians.htm>
- Creswell, W. J (2012). *Educational Research Planning, Conducting and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research* (4th ed.). Boston, MA: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Creswell, W. J (2014). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed). California: SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, W. J., Clark, P.L.V (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed). New Delhi, India: SAGE Publications India Pvt. Ltd.
- Crofts, M. (2012). Running an Open-Air Concert. Retrieved from <https://www.soundonsound.com/techniques/running-open-air-concert>
- Eisele, A. (2019). Live sound 101: Sound system design and setup for a live band. Retrieved from <https://www.bhphotovideo.com/explora/proaudio/buying-guide/live-sound-101-sound-system-design-and-setup-for-a-live-band>
- Encyclopedia.com (2019). Sound engineering technician. Retrieved from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/economics/news-and-education-magazines/sound-engineering-technician>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014). *National policy on education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Ministry of Railways, Government of India (2012). *Maintenance handbook on public address system*. Indian Railway Centre for Advanced Maintenance Technology. Retrieved from <https://rdso.indianrailways.gov.in/works/uploads/File/Main>

- [tenance%20handbook%20on%20Publ ic%20Address%20System.pdf](#)
- Fraenkel, R.J., Wallen, E.N. & Hyun, H.H. (2012). *How to design and evaluate research in education* (8th ed). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- Gay, R.L., Mills, E.G. & Airasian, P. (2012). *Educational research competencies for analysis and applications* (10th ed). New Jersey, NJ: Pearson Education, Inc.
- Locsin, A. (2019). Sound engineer qualifications. Retrieved from <https://work.chron.com/sound-engineer-qualifications-15984.html>
- Mega Public Address System (2018). Product guide. Retrieved from www.megaindia.in
- National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2001, pp. 1-75). *Radio, TV and Electronic work: National technical certificate (NTC) and advanced national technical certificate (ANTC) curriculum and course specifications*. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0016/001613/161374e.pdf>
- Nisbett, A. (2003). *The sound studio, audio: Audio techniques for radio, television, film and recording* (7th ed). Focal Press, Oxford, UK.
- Ogbuanya, T. C. (2009). *Energy and technology of home appliances*. Enugu: Cheston Ltd.
- Onwuegbuzie, J.A. & Leech, L. N. (2006). Linking research questions to mixed methods data analysis procedures. *The Qualitative Report*, 11(3): 474-498.
- Palme, C. (2019). Audio preventative maintenance for audio & video systems Retrieved from <https://www.sound solutionscanada.com>
- Parts-express (2016). Stadium PA installation instruction. Retrieved from <https://www.parts-express.com/pedocs/installation-guides/stadium-pa-installationinstructions.pdf>
- Solomon, K (2018). Design and construction of public address system. Retrieved from <https://afribary.com/works/design-and-construction-of-public-address-system-8695>
- Tayal, S. P (2012). Sound Reinforcement System: *International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering & Technology (IJSRET)*, 1(4), 064-068
- Tapia, C & Lyons, C (2016). Audio Systems Guide for meetings and conferences: A Shure Educational Publication
- Truity (2019). Broadcast or sound engineering technician. Retrieved from <https://www.truity.com/career-profile/broadcast-or-sound-engineering-technician>
- UNESCO-UNEVOC (2019). TVET country profile: Nigeria. Retrieved from https://unevoc.unesco.org/wtdb/worldvetdatabase_nga_en.pdf
- Uwaifo, O.V. & Uwaifo, U.I. (2009). Training technology and vocational education teachers for the new 9-3-4 education system in Nigeria: Its problems and prospects. *International NGO Journal*, 4(4), 160-166.